

AI's role in enhancing the capabilities of Chemists

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ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has surpassed human intelligence and is emerging as a momentous change in the discipline of synthetic chemistry. AI techniques are assisting chemists in exploring the vast theoretical space of chemical synthesis. This perspective discusses the modifications and transformations that have been achieved in the synthesis of any molecule after the emergence of AI. The significance of AI in combination with Deep Learning and Artificial Neural Networks in chemical synthesis has also been explained using examples. The role of AI in finding retrosynthetic pathways, predicting complex reactions, and synthesis of chemical moieties and drugs has been highlighted.

KEYWORDS

1. Artificial Intelligence, 2. Neural Networks. 3. Synthetic Methods, 4. Machine Learning, 5. Computational Chemistry

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INTRODUCTION

The advent of technology in the field of science has not only refined the efficiency of scientists but has also become an integral part of our lives. The promising benefits of technological developments have assisted the scientific community to achieve new milestones in every domain of research. In the past two years, humankind has witnessed the most fierce and deadliest COVID-19 pandemic. To combat this pandemic, researchers worldwide have put in exemplary efforts to design effective drugs in minimal time. This coherent drug designing was achievable with the assistance of Artificial Intelligence (AI). The tedious task of understanding complex structural activity relations and screening drug analogs has been eased using AI. The evolution of AI techniques and Machine Learning (ML) in drug discovery & design has benefited the entire population and continues to aid researchers with their experimentation in multifarious ways.

AI is that fabrication of human beings that has transfigured into a benison and its bloom has swayed every sphere of human life. It is sometimes referred to as Machine Learning (ML) or Deep Learning (DL) as it produces the desirable outcomes after learning from existing data. ML is a way to apply algorithms that helps the computer system in learning from a given set of data instances and some underlying assumptions. It enhances the ability of computers to perform those tasks which are not even defined in the code. This technological advancement in the field of chemistry has helped in various new inventions and synthesis of chemicals. AI can thus, serve as a valuable tool in bringing about sweeping change for scientists and researchers in designing, discovering, and developing new molecules.

Chemists spend most of their time synthesizing and characterizing novel chemical compounds and the process is arduous. Only a few hundred million compounds are known to date, which is an exceedingly small part of the estimated 10^{60} chemical molecules that can exist. To study and synthesize even one-billionth of these undiscovered compounds appears to be an impossible idea. However, the arrival of quantitative structure-activity models and data analysis methods in AI is ameliorating the quest of gripping new molecules and to study their properties and cardinal particulars. Computer-aided chemical synthesis has transformed

the most widely used tools and techniques like crystallization, distillation, vacuum filtration, and many more into automated processes that are reinventing chemistry.ⁱ AI, thus, acts as the connecting dot between the known and possible existing structures to expand the chemical universe for mankind.

This article's focal points are the vast and whopping applications of AI-based algorithms in the discipline of chemistry and chemical synthesis. This, therefore, presents our perspective on how AI is emerging as an asset in synthetic chemistry and depicts its efficiency in amplifying the competence of chemists.

1. THE CONTRIBUTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN SYNTHETIC PROCESSES

AI techniques have set foot in every domain of human society and are successfully used in varied disciplines including synthetic chemistry. The commencement of computer-aided synthesis for expertizing new synthetic methods is a gift of AI. The emerging technologies in AI can perform multistep reactions under optimized conditions and faster rate with less human input. The onset of predicting techniques in the field of chemistry, due to the advent of quantum chemical approaches and AI algorithms, is also significant.ⁱⁱ

1.1. Artificial Neural Networks

Using AI, chemists can excel in the disciplines of molecular and drug discovery, one-pot reactions, etc. Alongside, the utility of neural networks to translate reactants into the most suitable products is a boon for scientists for swinging synthetic processes. Neural network analysis is based on non-algorithmic information processing using probabilistic techniques and logistic regressions.ⁱⁱⁱ These neural networks concatenate the fingerprints of input reactants which are then utilized for the prediction of reactions and product molecules (**Figure 1**). The structure matching languages like SMILES (Simplified Molecular-Input Line- Entry System) and SMART (SMILES Arbitrary Targeted Specification)^{iv} are a few of the advances in AI which can lead to the development of streamlined reaction optimization and rapid synthesis. On this account, the utilization of AI can help in predicting the appropriate reaction type with greater accuracy. In our vision, the introduction of algorithms that can predict reaction mechanisms would further increase the efficiency and reliability of these neural networks.

Figure 1 : Human neuron and biological synapse's comparison with Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)

1.2. Computer-Aided Synthesis Planning

The AI and ML-based approaches have evinced the success of Computer-aided synthesis planning (CASP) in proposing chemical synthetic routes.^v Access to this synthetic route planning software bestows us with a stand-alone graphical user interface (GUI) that permits even the common users to interact with the suggested routes and predictions. Incorporating CASP software like ASKCOS, researchers can synthesize the desired products from commercially available reactants that are like those in reported routes.^{vi} In our consideration, employing such iterative software can help the researchers in eliminating those reaction routes which cannot be used in practice. These can help in predicting reaction routes in a more unbiased and economical manner. Thus, the strategy can be extremely productive upon execution in laboratories.

1.3. Fingerprint Descriptors for Chemical Properties Evaluation

The different processing of ML algorithms makes it possible to predict energetically favorable and viable reaction routes under specified reaction conditions. Data like vibrational or rotational spectrum or dipole moment for yield estimation is an example that possibly would not be considered by chemists, but by AI.^{vii} The use of well-established fingerprints as descriptors, like Morgan fingerprints and Tanimoto index, can be of great help in identifying molecular properties like HOMO-LUMO energy gaps, protein-ligand binding affinity, and

accessibility of synthesis routes for any novel molecule.^{viii} This ability of AI to foster physicochemical descriptors that harmonize with the electronic properties of molecules can assist in understanding the unaccomplished synthesis process as well. Thus, ML-enabled binary coding, computer-aided synthetic planning, and robotically executed reactions can facilitate real-time assessment using NMR and IR spectroscopy as well as the scale-up and production goals.

There are software like Elaboration of Reactions for Organic Synthesis (EROS), System for Organic Reaction Prediction by Heuristic Approach (SOPHIA) that have evolved (Figure 2), and takes the assistance of bond polarity, electro negativity across the molecule, the resonance effect, etc.^{ix} for predicting reaction outcomes using nominal user input reactants.^x Similarly, Synthia is software that has been used to find routes for the synthesis of medicinally relevant compounds with improved yields. It is thus, noteworthy to increase our cognizance of the primacy of AI in drug designing and synthesis.^{xi} Utilization of tools like Reaction Predictor,^{xii} which assists in predicting the outcome of reactions, can prove to be a vanguard in analyzing diverse types of chemical processes involving electrophiles and nucleophiles, pericyclic reactions or oxidizing, reducing, and free radical species.

Figure 2 : Different software, neural networks, databases, and fingerprint descriptors.

1.4. Three-Dimensional Structure Visualization

AI has an additional advantage not only in retrosynthesis but in visualizing the 3D structures of molecules as well. The chemical abstract service (CAS) registry has multiple molecules for which the properties and structures (2D and 3D) are pre-recorded. This data can be utilized to predict the 3D structure of any new molecule. There are several *de novo* 3D structures designing software that stimulates 3D structure visualization of novel molecules and drugs based on previously stored data.^{xiii} According to our perception, more algorithms should be designed and utilized to predict chemical reactions based on the structure of compounds to enhance the rate of synthesis. This can also aid chemists in understanding when to abort a reaction if an unwanted/ side product is forming and in the determination of an analogous pathway for a particular reaction to obtain the specified product.^{xiv}

1.5. Multi-Parameter Analysis

The multi-processing characteristic of AI is also of immense utility in chemical synthesis. The ability of computers to perform multiple analyses simultaneously makes the study of multi-parameters reactions uncomplicated. The multiparameter interactions taking place in any chemical reaction are better visualized by ML than manual studies and optimizations. More the knowledge regarding the effect of various parameters better can be the yield and quality of chemical products synthesized.^{xv}

1.6. Automated Continuous Flow Process

Continuous flow processing is a discipline that has led to the miniaturization of synthetic processes along with their automation. However, there are extremely limited databases available that provide information about the optimization of continuous flow processes. AI-driven works can aid the chemists in determining whether a reaction is suitable for continuous flow and foretell the alternative components. This, in turn, can encourage chemists to explore a more coherent computer-aided continuous flow synthesis of compounds. The designing and production of new compounds can be done at a faster rate using continuous flow and the obtained data can be recorded in digital/electronic files

(Figure 3). Available databases can facilitate the selection of appropriate solvents, temperature parameters, and thus enhance reaction efficacy. Thus, the synergism of AI and continuous flow can lead to greener, smarter, and more sustainable methods for compound synthesis.

Figure 3: Reaction optimization and data recording using AI in a standard continuous flow protocol.

1.7. Retrosynthetic Pathways Predication

The use of AI in retrosynthesis can be another stupendous contribution to chemistry. The complex ML algorithms are inculcated with a huge database that can help in developing a retrosynthesis tree for the target molecule/compound. From LHASA (Logic and Heuristics Applied to Synthetic Analysis)^{xvi} to the combinational use of ML-based deep learning algorithms such as that in Monte Carlo tree search^{xvii}, there are several AI-based tools for retrosynthesis. These algorithms can present propitious retrosynthetic steps many folds faster than human-generated retrosynthesis (Figure 4). Tools like “Ring Breaker” also help in predicting ring-forming or breaking strategies that can help in reinventing retrosynthetic and synthetic chemical routes. Thus, by incorporation of ML and deep learning-based algorithms, the retrosynthetic routes can be devised in a trice.^{xviii}

Though several advances have been made already and many more are under progress, in our perception, molecular designing with desired properties is still a challenge. The analysis of a plethora of information, management of huge databases of molecular properties and reactions, can be done effectively using AI. Databases provided by PubChem, ZINC, ChEMBL, etc., for instance, give access to information about hundreds of millions of compounds. These databases can function as precursors or descriptors to predict the properties of any newly synthesized molecule. These can also assist the chemists in the synthesis of a larger number of library compounds or molecular analogs of previously existing or new molecules.^{xix}

Figure 4: Retrosynthetic tree formation and prediction of suitable precursors using ML algorithms

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larger number of library compounds or molecular analogs of previously existing or new molecules.^{xx}

1.8. AI-Stimulated Small Drug Molecule Synthesis

The amalgamation of AI with Chemistry has resulted in an efficient process of drug development despite the complexities involved in the process. The computer-aided small molecular drug discovery and development methods and ML methods are being used for building predictive models such as quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) models, Drug-Target Interactions (DTIs), generating novel molecules, and prediction of the physicochemical and toxicological properties of the drug molecule.^{xxi} With development of AI techniques a design-make-test-analysis (DMTA) cycle is also used in small molecular drug discovery and its analysis.¹⁹

1.9. Microwave Heating using AI

Microwave heating has varied applications in chemical synthesis. The electromagnetic radiations of microwave frequency are used for providing appropriate heat to initiate and complete chemical reactions. However, there are very few advancements made to date that can help chemists in deciding the appropriate temperature and time conditions to be set. The estimated time and temperature parameters can be incorrect and might result in inappropriate results. AI can play a significant role in this process. The use of thermal imaging methods and deep learning can transform this hypothesized temperature setting to automatic temperature recommendation. Deep learning can result in learning from the obtained thermal images for future prediction of temperatures for similar reactions. In our viewpoint, this amalgamation of AI and microwave can lead to more precise reaction parameters.^{xxii}

The use of ML can thus, help us transform the age-old process of “deductive learning” which is producing data based on learned theory, to “inductive learning” which involves the collection of data to generate information.^{xxiii} This prowess of ML algorithm to privies novel and unprecedented knowledge with the help of characteristics of existing paths is very promising. Taking advantage of active learning for predicting the suitable conditions

for any reaction using AI acts as a shot in the arm for scientists for synthesizing any new molecule. AI acts as an asset in tracking down the readily available building blocks that make the synthetic process timesaving, labour-saving, and cost-effective.^{xxiv}

CONCLUSION

In this era of “big data,” the benefits and utilities of Artificial Intelligence in synthetic chemistry are numerous. The aspiration of chemists to build up the modernistic world of chemistry and to streamline the process can be fulfilled by leveraging AI techniques. In the discipline of chemistry, though AI is still at a primitive stage, there is a substantial increase in works related to ML and deep learning. The researchers and stakeholders are working progressively upon the limitations such as appropriate data availability, database management, algorithm development, etc. These progressions, indeed, are transforming the labour-intensive chemical synthesis methods to AI-assisted synthesis. Advancements in various AI and ML-based tools are enhancing the ability of chemists to craft, synthesize and study any novel compound. Thus, in our viewpoint, AI can enable synthetic chemists in excelling synthesis processes and can be the leading light for the future of chemistry.

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